

**THE USE OF MALEIC ANHYDRIDE MODIFIED POLYPROPYLENE
FOR PERFORMANCE ENHANCEMENT IN
CONTINUOUS GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (m-PP) on static mechanical properties of continuous glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (PP) composites. Maleic anhydride modified polypropylene was added to the PP homopolymer to improve the adhesion between the matrix and the glass fibre. Three-point bending tests were performed on 0° and 90° unidirectional glass fibre/PP laminates with different weight fractions m-PP in the PP matrix. These tests showed an increase in both longitudinal and transverse flexural strength up to 10 wt.% m-PP, whereas at higher weight fractions m-PP a decrease in flexural strength was observed. No significant influence of m-PP on composite stiffness was observed.

Keywords: glass fibre, polypropylene, adhesion, interface, chemically modified polypropylene, mechanical properties

1. INTRODUCTION

The cost effectiveness of a structure depends not only on performance or manufacturing costs, but also on raw material costs. Consequently, the economic potential of continuous fibre reinforced composites based on glass fibres and commodity plastics like poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET), polyamide (PA) and polypropylene (PP) may attract, in combination with the potential advantage of high production rates, large volume markets such as automotive industries. Nowadays, thermoplastic 'bulk' composites have two established technologies: first, short fibre reinforced injection moulding compounds and second, glass mat thermoplastics (GMT's), being stampable sheet products based on moderate loadings of relatively long fibres in random array [1]. Recently, there have been some activities in the field of continuous glass fibre reinforced composites based on commodity thermoplastics [2], to fill the gap between high-performance composite systems such as PEEK/carbon based APC-2 and GMT's with relatively limited performance.

An important aspect with regard to the performance and durability of fibre reinforced thermoplastics is the adhesion between the fibre and the matrix. Since poor adhesion usually results in poor composite properties, there is a growing interest in composite research focussing on interfacial phenomena and its effect on composite performance [3-5]. The interaction between the matrix and the fibre can be improved by using a fibre with a sizing specific to the polymer matrix. In case of glass fibres, organofunctional silanes may be used as adhesion promoters between the organic matrix and the glass fibre [6]. Apolar polymers such as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) have limited interaction with a sizing specific for these polymers. To resolve this problem, the PP should be modified to increase the interaction between the matrix and the sized fibre. Fibre/matrix systems, that can be used to receive optimum adhesion between the fibres and the matrix, are acrylic acid grafted PP and maleic anhydride modified PP in combination with glass fibre with compatible sizings. Such a sizing, containing amide groups, can increase the interaction between the PP matrix and the glass fibre by chemical reaction [7].

Studies on the influence of acrylic acid grafted PP on the mechanical properties of short glass fibre reinforced polypropylene compounds showed that the performance of such materials can be improved by addition of chemically modified PP [8]. Recently, the development of such chemically modified PP's resulted in the introduction of a second generation GMT sheet with better adhesion between the fibres and the matrix.

This paper deals with the influence of maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (m-PP) on the mechanical properties of continuous glass fibre reinforced PP composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

In this study we used a continuous glass fibre of PPG Industries Fiber Glass by (PPG 854) and a polypropylene matrix (homopolymer VM6100, Melt Flow Index: 20) of Shell Chemicals. To increase the interfacial bond strength between the glass fibre and the PP matrix, a maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (m-PP) of BP Chemicals Ltd. (Polybond 3002) was added to the PP matrix. The weight fraction m-PP in the PP matrix of the specimens was varied between 0 wt.% and 100 wt.%.

Unidirectional (UD) laminates were manufactured by a film stacking method, where fibres are wound on a rectangular mandrel with alternating layers of polymer films which were prepared in various compositions using film blowing equipment (Figure 1). A typical laminate with a thickness of 2 mm consisted of approximately 10 layers of fibres with alternating layers of polymer film. The material was melted at 200°C and pressed for 45 minutes at 25 bar. After hot-pressing, the composites were slowly cooled in the hot-press

resulting in laminates with a fibre volume fraction of 58%, showing good overall impregnation and wet out of fibres.

Figure 1. Manufacturing of UD-laminates by film stacking method.

Test specimens were cut from the UD-composite plates. To remove cutting irregularities, specimen edges were subjected to several grinding operations.

2.3 Testing

Three-point bending tests were performed according to ASTM D-790 on a Frank tensile machine, type 81565. The span-to-depth ratio of the 2 mm thick specimens was 40 by using a span of 80 mm. The width of the test specimens for longitudinal and transverse testing was 12 and 25 mm respectively. The test speed was 5 mm/min.

During flexural testing of 90° specimens, damage initiation and development was real-time monitored using an acoustic emission system (PAC 8900 Locan AT) of Physical Acoustics Corp., including a 40 dB pre-amplifier (PAC 1200A).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The longitudinal and transverse flexural properties of UD-glass/PP composites are summarized in Table 1 for different weight fractions m-PP in the PP matrix. Also included in this Table are the mechanical properties of the pure polymer matrix as determined by tensile testing of specimens with different compositions. Experiments on unreinforced polymers showed no negative effects of the addition of m-PP on the tensile strength of m-PP/PP blends. However, since the morphology and consequently the properties of a crystalline polymer such as PP are influenced by the presence of glass fibres [9], it is difficult to relate neat resin properties as listed in Table 1 to the properties of the polymer matrix in a real composite.

3.1 Transverse flexural properties

Approximate linear elastic behaviour up to fracture of the composite was observed for all specimens. A comparison of the transverse flexural strengths of the glass fibre/PP

composites with different weight fractions m-PP is shown Figure 2. The transverse flexural strength increased up to 10 wt.% m-PP with 240 %, whereas at higher weight fractions m-PP a decrease in transverse strength was observed.

Table 1. Flexural properties of the glass/PP composites and tensile properties of PP matrix at different weight fractions m-PP in the PP matrix.

weight perc. m-PP	0	5	10	20	40	60	100
composite							
$\sigma_{trans.}$ (MPa)	8.6	14.6	20.6	10.6	12.7	15.0	14.8
$\sigma_{long.}$ (MPa)	774	806	1037	720	620	800	740
$E_{trans.}$ (GPa)	4.9	6.0	6.8	5.4	5.8	6.8	6.4
$E_{long.}$ (GPa)	38.5	36.5	32.0	33.6	35.8	31.8	32.6
$\epsilon_{trans.}$ (%)	0.15	0.24	0.31	0.23	0.22	0.24	0.23
$\epsilon_{long.}$ (%)	2.11	2.31	3.34	2.24	1.83	2.60	2.37
matrix							
σ (MPa)	27.5	29.0	29.4	29.2	28.8	33.2	32.3
E (GPa)	1.5	1.5	1.7	1.5	1.7	1.5	1.6
ϵ (%)	5.3	5.0	5.1	5.6	4.0	9.7	9.8

Figure 2. Transverse flexural strength of glass/PP composites as a function of the weight fraction m-PP in the PP matrix.

Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces of failed specimens (Figure 3a-c) showed a change in failure mode from interface failure for composites with 0 wt.% m-PP to matrix fracture for composites based on a 10 wt.% m-PP matrix, whereas at 100 wt.% m-PP again interface failure was observed (Figure 3c). However, some evidence of thin layers of matrix material on the surface of the glass fibre suggested that besides interface failure also matrix or 'interphase' failure occurred.

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrographs of transverse fracture surfaces showing: (a) interface failure at 0 wt.% m-PP, (b) matrix failure at 10 wt.% m-PP and (c) a combination of interphase and matrix failure at 100 wt.% m-PP.

The typical case of matrix fracture for composites with 10 wt.% m-PP and a transverse composite strength close to that of the pure resin, indicated that an optimum in interaction between the matrix and the fibre was reached and that composite properties for this system are matrix dominated rather than interface dominated. Consequently, a further increase in the amount of m-PP will not result in a further increase in fibre/matrix bond strength. However, this would also imply a constant transverse strength rather than a decrease if we assume that the amount of m-PP has no influence on the matrix or interphase properties. Since, at higher (>10 wt.%) weight fractions m-PP, a decrease in transverse strength was observed, addition of m-PP also seems to reduce the matrix and/or interphase properties and consequently the transverse properties of the composites.

In general, the transverse flexural modulus of the composites was not significantly influenced by the amount of m-PP, except for the flexural modulus of the glass/PP composite with 0% m-PP (Table 1). This might be caused by interfacial changes, like the formation of a more brittle interphase, due to the addition of m-PP. However, since the deviation in moduli is rather high, care should be taken on drawing conclusions from these data.

The cumulative plots of events versus time of all types of glass/PP composites are shown in Figure 4. The increase in strain to failure also resulted in an increase in the onset of damage for composites based on a matrix with 10 wt.% m-PP. Composites with 10 wt.% m-PP showed a rapid increase in emissions at a approximately 65% of the maximum load, whereas composites with 0 wt.% m-PP showed an onset of damage at approximately 30% of the maximum load.

Figure 4. Cumulative AE plots of different transversely loaded glass/PP composites.

3.2 Longitudinal flexural properties

When comparing the longitudinal flexural moduli of the different composites, no significant difference is observed (Table 1). Improved adhesion has no significant influence on the longitudinal composite modulus because this composite property is primarily

dominated by the modulus of the fibre and its volume fraction.

The longitudinal flexural strengths (Figure 5), and the failure modes of the different glass/PP composites, showed the same trend as those of transversely tested composites. The fibres in a composite with 0 wt.% m-PP were completely free of matrix material with the fibres not held together by the matrix, indicating extensive interfacial fracture. In the 100 wt.% m-PP composite, the failure modes were a combination of interface and matrix failure, whereas in the system with 10 wt.% m-PP, fibres were still covered by the polymer matrix, indicating relatively good stress transfer.

Figure 5. Longitudinal flexural strength of glass/PP composites as a function of the weight fraction m-PP in the PP matrix.

The increase in longitudinal strength and strain can be explained by greater effectiveness of the reinforcing fibres, due to an increase in fibre-matrix interaction in the composite system with 10 wt.% m-PP. Based on a rule of mixture relationship for the tensile strength of fibre reinforced composites, including an effectivity parameter k the influence of m-PP on the fibre efficiency can be demonstrated:

$$\sigma_c = k [\sigma_f V_f + E_m \epsilon_f (1 - V_f)] \quad (1)$$

where σ_c is the composite tensile strength, σ_f is the fibre tensile strength, E_m is the stiffness of the matrix, ϵ_f is the failure strain of the fibre and V_f is the fibre volume fraction. A typical value for the tensile strength of E-glass fibres as obtained from impregnated strand tests is approximately 2400 MPa. Using the matrix moduli as listed in Table 1, a fibre failure strain of 0.033 and a fibre volume fraction of 0.58, the effectivity parameter k yields values of 0.56 and 0.75 for composites with 0 wt.% and 10 wt.% m-PP respectively. However, even in the case of a 10 wt.% m-PP composite system, fibre efficiency is rather low in comparison with that of glass fibre reinforced systems based on epoxy resins, yielding values for k in the order of 0.90-0.95.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study showed an increase in composite strength due to the addition of maleic anhydride modified polypropylene to continuous glass fibre reinforced polypropylene composites. An optimum in both longitudinal and transverse flexural strength was reached for composites based on a PP matrix with 10 wt.% m-PP. Scanning electron micrographs showed a change in failure mode from debonding to matrix fracture for 10 wt.% m-PP composites, indicating an optimum in adhesion between the matrix and the fibre for this composite system. At higher weight fractions m-PP a decrease in flexural strength was observed, while fractographs showed again a change to more interfacial dominated failure modes.

These results indicated that besides the adhesion level between the matrix and the fibre, also the interphase and/or matrix properties were influenced by the addition of m-PP to the glass/PP composite, causing a decrease in strength at higher weight fractions m-PP.

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